

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The influence of work environment, work motivation on employee performance with intervening variables of job satisfaction of the Medan city library and archives service

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the relationship between work environment, work motivation, job satisfaction, and employee performance at Dinas Perpustakaan dan Kearsipan Kota Medan. The identified issues from the Strategic Plan Report of the Office serve as the research foundation. The research method employed non-probability sampling using a saturation sampling technique, involving the entire population of 64 employees at Dinas Perpustakaan dan Kearsipan Kota Medan. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with Smart Partial Least Squares (PLS) was utilized for data analysis. The findings indicate a significant positive relationship between the work environment and job satisfaction, as well as between work motivation and job satisfaction. Additionally, there is a significant positive influence of the work environment and work motivation on employee performance, and a positive significant impact of job satisfaction on employee performance. However, there is an exception in the relationship between the work environment and employee performance through job satisfaction, which is not significant. Conversely, work motivation significantly and positively influences employee performance through job satisfaction. This research contributes significantly to understanding the factors influencing employee performance Dinas Perpustakaan dan Kearsipan Kota Medan. Suggestions for further research include considering other variables that may affect the relationships studied and enhancing the quality and quantity of employees and facilities in the work environment.

Keywords: Work Environment; Work Motivation; Job Satisfaction; Employee Performance

1 Introduction

Organizations, both government and private, profit and non-profit, carry out performance to improve services and respond to the aspirations of the community and within the organization. Feedback from within the organization is important as feedback for improvement, in addition to accommodating aspirations, complaints, criticisms, and suggestions from the community. The performance of an employee has a crucial role in directing the elements of the organization to achieve the goals that have been set. According to [1], performance is the result of quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. Employee performance is measured based on the achievement of results in their work with certain criteria, influenced by the interaction of abilities and motivation [2].

Performance can be influenced by factors such as abilities and skills, knowledge, work design, personality, work motivation, leadership, leadership style, organizational culture, job satisfaction, work environment, loyalty, commitment, and work discipline [3]. One of the things that affects employee performance is the work environment. The work environment is all the work facilities and infrastructure around the employees who are doing work that can affect the implementation of work, this work environment includes the workplace, work facilities and infrastructure, cleanliness, lighting, tranquility, including work relationships between employees [4]. In this study [1], motivation is

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one of the things that affects employee performance. Work motivation is an encouragement of needs in employees that need to be met so that the employee can adjust to his environment and be able to achieve the goals that have been set. Research conducted by (Sutisna, 2021) and (Yanuari, 2019) shows that work motivation and work environment have an influence on employee performance.

Job satisfaction, as a subjective evaluation of work and the work environment, plays an important role in employee motivation (Sunarta, 2019). Employees who are satisfied with their jobs tend to perform better. Job satisfaction is the satisfaction of employees with their work between what employees expect from their work in their office [5]. According to [6] it, job satisfaction is an individual's general attitude towards his or her job.

The government as an organization in displaying high public service performance must be supported by available resources. The Medan City Library and Archives Service as an organization of the Regional apparatus of the Medan City Government must improve its performance in accordance with its vision and mission, the main one is in service. Initial observations at the Medan City Library and Archives Office showed that there were two separate office buildings, namely the library building and the archive building, with locations and distances that were quite far apart. This creates difficulties in coordination between fields, especially because the library building is affiliated with other agencies. In addition, the archive depot building is located in an asphalt burning area for road hotmix, causing inconvenience to employees. Room arrangements for employees and archival public services are also considered inadequate.

In support of this research, the following problems related to this research, which are described in the Strategic Plan Report (Renstra) of the Medan City Library and Archives Office for 2021-2026, which are related to the implementation of the following tasks:

- There is still a lack of availability of types of regional library materials and ancient manuscripts
- The lack of orderly handling of archives in the Regional Government and not all archives can be saved and the archives handed over are still chaotic
- Misperception of archives and archival responsibility.
- The function of the Archives Information System in archive management has not been optimal
- There is still a lack of availability of archive types in the form of documents, photos and audiovisuals.
- The quality and quantity of employees are inadequate in handling work in the field of libraries and archives in the city of Medan.

Facilities and infrastructure have not been maximally supported by all activities and services of the Medan City Library and Archives Office. The current condition of the library service room is only one and is used for all service activities which are very limited in scope (circulation room, children's room, reference, deposit); and the archive depot which is located unrepresentative because it is located at the asphalt manufacturing site.

Research carried out by Sutisna, (2021) that the work environment, work motivation and job satisfaction have a significant effect on employee performance. Aligned results found by [7], [8], [9].

There is a alignment of the findings from the survey with previous research which shows that the work environment, work motivation, and job satisfaction have a significant influence on employee performance. Thus, this study further explores these factors to better understand the problems and potential solutions that can be applied in improving the performance of employees of the Medan City Library and Archives Service.

1.1 Employee Performance

Performance or work achievement is the work result that a person has achieved based on his work behavior in carrying out activities at the workplace [10]. According to [11], performance is a real behavior that everyone displays as work achievements produced by employees in accordance with their role in the company. In addition, according to Wakhyuni (2018), performance is the result of a person's work function or activities in an organization that are influenced by various facts to achieve organizational goals in a certain period of time.

Factors that affect employee performance, according to [3], include:

- Ability and Expertise. The ability or skill that a person has in doing a job.
- Knowledge. Having knowledge about the job well will give good job results as well.
- Work Plan. Job designs that will make it easier for employees to achieve their goals
- Personality. A character that a person has.

- Work Motivation. Encouragement for someone to do the work.
- Leadership. The behavior of a leader in regulating, managing, and ordering his subordinates to do a task and responsibility given.
- Leadership Style. The attitude of a leader in facing or ordering his subordinates.
- Organizational Culture. Norms that apply and are owned by an organization or company.
- Job Satisfaction. A person's feelings before and after doing a job.
- Work Environment. The atmosphere or conditions around the workplace location.
- Loyalty. Employee loyalty to stay employed and defend the company where they work.
- Commitment
- Employee compliance with the promises he has made.
- Work Discipline
- Employees' efforts to carry out their work activities seriously

1.2 Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a feeling that supports or does not support employees related to their work or their own condition [1]. Job satisfaction is an attitude of employees or employees towards work related to work situations, cooperation between employees, rewards received at work, and other matters related to physical and psychological factors [12]. According to [4], factors that affect job satisfaction involve:

- Hope. Satisfaction occurs when expectations are met, while dissatisfaction arises when it is not met.
- Self-Assessment. Self-esteem and assessment of work affect employee attitudes and satisfaction.
- Social Norms. Attention from superiors or co-workers can provide encouragement and influence satisfaction.
- Social Comparison. Job differences can cause dissatisfaction through comparisons with others.
- Input or Output Relationship. Satisfaction depends on the employee's assessment of the relationship between job inputs and outputs.
- Bonding. Job choices and ties to companies affect satisfaction.
- Basis of Thought. Topics that are often discussed by fellow employees, such as salary, can affect job satisfaction.

1.3 Work Environment

According to [13], the work environment is the entire tool and materials that are faced, the surrounding environment where a person works, the working method, and the work arrangement both individually and as a group. The work environment is all the work facilities and infrastructure around the employees who are doing work that can affect the implementation of work, this work environment includes the workplace, work facilities and infrastructure, cleanliness, lighting, tranquility, including work relationships between employees (Hasibuan, 2018). According to Sedarmayanti (2017), broadly speaking, the type of work environment is divided into two factors, namely physical work environment factors and non-physical work environment factors.

- Physical Work Environment Factors; Coloring, Lighting, Air, Noise, Motion space
- Security
- Hygiene
- b. Non-Physical Work Environment Factors
- Work structure
- Job responsibilities
- Leader's attention and support

1.4 Work Motivation

Work motivation according to [1] is an encouragement of needs in employees that needs to be met so that the employee can adjust to his environment and be able to achieve the goals that have been set. The motivation for the implementation of work by an employee in a company basically takes place in the condition of the employee as a human being, where the inner and psychological atmosphere of an employee in his work environment has a great influence on the performance of his duties (Rahayu, 2018). According to [14], work motivation is a driving force that results in an employee being willing and willing to mobilize his ability to form expertise and skills, manpower and time to carry out various activities that are his responsibility and fulfill his obligations in order to achieve the company's goals and various goals that have been predetermined.

There are two factors that affect work motivation according to (Prihartanta, 2015), namely intersthetic and extrinsic motivation.

1.5 Intrinsic Motivation

Refers to the impulse or motivation that comes from within the individual itself, not from external factors. This motivation arises from the intrinsic satisfaction obtained from the task or activity itself. Examples are a sense of accomplishment, satisfaction with the work done, or a deep interest in the field of work.

1.6 Extrinsic Motivation

Impulses or motivations that come from external factors, not from the intrinsic desire or satisfaction of the task or activity itself. This motivation arises from rewards or rewards obtained from outside the individual, such as recognition, status, or financial rewards. Examples are high salaries, job promotions, or recognition of work achievements.

2 Methodology

2.1 Research Approach

This type of research is associative research with a quantitative method which is a research method based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research on a specific population or sample, data collection using research instruments [15]. Associative research is a study that analyzes the relationship between two or more variables, [16]. Research links cause or effect. YAMG analyzed the independent variable, mediation variable and the dependent variable that was affected. The causal relationship arising from the independent variables is (X1) Work Environment, (X2) Work Motivation, mediation variable (Z) Job Satisfaction, and bound variable (Y) Employee Performance at the Medan City Library and Archives Service.

2.2 Population & Sample

The population of this study is 64 employees of the Medan City Library and Archives Office. Non-probability sampling is selected in the research sampling technique with saturated sampling, which is a method of drawing samples when all members of the population are used as samples. Therefore, all the populations sampled in this study amounted to 64 people. Sampling with a saturated sample, that is, all populations are sampled in this study [15].

2.3 Variable Operational Definition

According to [15], operational definition is an important process in research that involves determining the concept or properties to be investigated and turning them into variables that can be measured concretely.

2.4 Data Collection Techniques

In this study, two types of data were used, namely primary data and secondary data. Primary data refers to data that comes from researchers for the first time, such as interviews, observations, and questionnaires. Secondary data is data that already exists, collected by previous investigators of agencies and organizations.

This research was carried out three data collections, namely observation, questionnaire, and documentation study. Observation is the systematic observation and recording of the symptoms that appear in the research object. A questionnaire or questionnaire is a data collection technique that is carried out by giving a set of questions or written statements to respondents to be answered. Document study is a data collection technique by collecting and analyzing documents, both written documents, images, works, and electronics [15].

In this study, the Likert scale was used to measure respondents' attitudes, opinions, and perceptions related to the social phenomena studied [15]. The Likert Scale allows each respondent to give their assessment of a statement or question using the rating range provided. This approach provides a systematic framework for measuring complex variables, such as work environment, work motivation, job satisfaction, and employee performance in this study.

2.5 Data Analysis Techniques

This study uses the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method with Smart Partial Least Squares (PLS), an approach to structural equation models based on components or variants. SEM is a field of statistical study that allows testing a series of relationships that are difficult to measure simultaneously. SEM analysis with PLS consists of three stages: 1)

Outer model analysis, 2) Inner model analysis, and 3) Hypothesis testing. The overall evaluation of the PLS model is carried out by considering both the outer model and the inner model.[17]

2.5.1 *Outer Model*

In the outer model, the validity of the construct is evaluated using convergent validity and discriminant validity with the value of Average Variance Extracted (AVE). The AVE value should be ≥ 0.5 to indicate sufficient validity. Reliability was tested using two methods, namely Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability. For the external factor charge value, a \geq value of 0.4 is accepted, while a reliability value should be ≥ 0.7 to indicate good internal consistency.[17]

2.5.2 *Inner Model*

In the inner model analysis, the value of the path coefficient or inner model is used to evaluate the significance of the causal relationship between latent variables. The standardized value of the path coefficient showed the magnitude of the influence of exogenous variables on endogenous variables, and the T-statistical value was above 1.96 for testing the two-tailed hypothesis and above 1.64 for the one-tailed hypothesis at $\alpha = 5\%$. Hypothesis testing is carried out by bootstrapping method, and the significance of the influence of independent variables on dependent variables and independent variables on mediation variables must be met. The determination coefficient (R²) was used to analyze the ability of the independent variable model to explain the variance of the dependent variable data, with a criterion value of 0.75; 0.5; 0.25 which rated the model as good, medium, and weak, respectively. Adjusted R² is used when examining exogenous variables with different measurements or different number of observations.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Overview of the Medan City Library and Archives Service

The Medan City Library was established in 1972 based on the Decree of the Mayor of the Medan Level II Regional Municipality No. 839/1972 dated December 27, 1972. The main purpose of the establishment of this library is to form the Medan City Regional Public Library Center which has several crucial functions. First, this library provides materials that are considered necessary to be known by the wider community. This paper is used to support the development of the city of Medan in various fields, including the results of seminars, symposiums, musda, regional decisions/regulations, government, and speeches in official ceremonies. Second, the library provides services in the form of educational materials and other materials that are useful for spiritual and civic mental development based on Pancasila.

In addition, this library provides services to the general public, students, and students in meeting the needs of scientific and educational resources in accordance with the curriculum, starting from elementary school to tertiary level. This is done to improve the quality of education and teaching in the Medan Municipality area. The library also provides a forum for all levels of society to follow the development of the country and the world in various fields through newspapers, magazines, and brochures, as well as provide reading entertainment with pedagogical value, which is beneficial for the spiritual development of children and the future of the younger generation. In addition, this library is in charge of fostering, supervising, and coordinating public libraries held in various areas of Medan Municipality.

Currently, the Medan City Public Library has been renamed the Medan City Library and Archives. The vision of the Medan City Library and Archives is to create a reliable library to form a Medan community that has a reading culture and love of books. The mission includes improving the quality and quantity of School Libraries, Special Libraries, and Community Libraries, creating a community that likes to read and love books, and increasing community participation in the existence of libraries. With these various efforts, the Medan City Library and Archives is committed to continuing to be a reliable center for information and education, as well as building an intelligent and insightful society through a reading culture.

3.2 SEM-PLS Statistical Analysis

3.2.1 *Outer Model*

In the SEM-PLS method, the evaluation of convergent validity is carried out through outer loading. Validity is considered satisfied if each indicator has an outer load that exceeds 0.7 against the relevant latent variable, according to the guidelines of Hair et al. (2019). Convergent validity shows the extent to which the indicator reflects the latent variable and supports the accuracy of the construction of the variable.

Source: Research Results, 2024

Figure 1 Outer Model Results

After conducting a validity test using SmartPLS 4.0, it can be seen in Figure 4.1 that all indicators are considered valid because they have an outer loading value that exceeds 0.7 (> 0.7). This shows that these indicators well reflect the latent variables measured and can be trusted for further analysis.

3.2.2 Outer Loading Value

In the data presented, the value of the loading factor (*outer loading*) of the latent variable indicator used in the study on average exceeded 0.7, in accordance with the recommendation. This indicates that these indicators effectively reflect the latent variables being measured, indicating good quality in the measurement of those variables.

Table 1 Outer Loading Results

	Kepuasan Kerja (Z)	Kinerja Pegawai (Y)	Lingkungan Kerja (X1)	Motivasi Kerja (X3)
KIP1		0.903		
KIP2		0.915		
KIP3		0.876		
KIP4		0.898		
KIP5		0.896		
KIP6		0.912		
KSK1	0.913			
KSK2	0.926			
KSK3	0.925			
KSK4	0.944			
KSK5	0.952			
KSK6	0.950			

LIK1			0.964	
LIK2			0.920	
LIK3			0.904	
LIK4			0.924	
LIK5			0.940	
LIK6			0.952	
MOV1				0.934
MOV2				0.935
MOV3				0.883
MOV4				0.916
MOV5				0.901
MOV6				0.888

Source: Research Results, 2024

3.2.3 Average Variance Extract (AVE), Composite Reliability & Cronbach's Alpha Test

Average Variance Extraction (AVE), Composite Reliability, and Cronbach's Alpha are important steps in evaluating the quality of latent variable measurements in confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) or construct validation. AVE (Average Variance Extracted) is a parameter used to assess the validity of latent variable convergence. If the AVE value of a variable exceeds 0.5, it indicates that the variable is considered valid (Ghozali & Latan, 2015).

Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha are used to evaluate the internal reliability or consistency of the constructed being measured. A value above 0.7 is generally considered good in both of these tests (Ghozali & Latan, 2015). The test results in the table show that the indicators and variables in this study are eligible for the reliability test. Therefore, the data will be further tested on the Inner model for more in-depth analysis.

Table 2 Average Variance Extract (AVE), Composite Reliability & Cronbach's Alpha Test

	Cronbach' alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Kepuasan Kerja (Z)	0.971	0.972	0.977	0.874
Kinerja Pegawai (Y)	0.953	0.953	0.962	0.810
Lingkungan Kerja (X1)	0.971	0.971	0.976	0.873
Motivasi Kerja (X3)	0.958	0.959	0.967	0.828

Source: Research Results, 2024

The results of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE), Composite Reliability, and Cronbach's Alpha tests are as follows:

- Job Satisfaction (Z): AVE = 0.874, Cronbach's alpha = 0.971, Composite reliability (rho_a) = 0.972, Composite reliability (rho_c) = 0.977.
- Employee Performance (Y): AVE = 0.810, Cronbach's alpha = 0.953, Composite reliability (rho_a) = 0.953, Composite reliability (rho_c) = 0.962.
- Working Environment (X1): AVE = 0.873, Cronbach's alpha = 0.971, Composite reliability (rho_a) = 0.971, Composite reliability (rho_c) = 0.976.
- Work Motivation (X2): AVE = 0.828, Cronbach's alpha = 0.958, Composite reliability (rho_a) = 0.959, Composite reliability (rho_c) = 0.967.

All variables showed an AVE value of more than 0.5, indicating good convergence validity. In addition, Cronbach's alpha and high Composite reliability values, which are above 0.7, indicate an adequate level of reliability for each latent variable.

3.2.4 Inner Model

Figure 2 Inner Model Results

Source: Research Results, 2024

The next SEM-PLS test is to test the inner model (structural model) with the aim of analyzing the influence of the relationship between the variables used and testing the hypothesis based on its significance value.

3.3 Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Analysis of the determination coefficient of R-square (R²) is used to evaluate how well the independent variable explains the variation in the bound variable:

Table 3 Determination Coefficient (R²) Results

R-square	R-square adjusted
0.973	0.972
0.955	0.953

Source: Research Results, 2024

The *R-square adjusted value* for the Job Satisfaction variable (Y) is 0.972, indicating that Work Environment (X1) and Work Motivation (X2), together, are able to explain about 97.2% of the variation in Employee Performance (Y). These results confirm that the model has a strong ability to understand the factors that affect Employee Performance (Y). The remaining 2.8% of variation may be explained by other factors that have not yet been studied, such as work stress or leadership style.

Similarly, the Employee Performance variable (Y) has an *Adjusted R-square value* of 0.953. This shows that Work Environment (X1) and Work Motivation (X2) are able to explain about 95.3% of the variation in Employee Performance (Y). These findings reaffirm the effectiveness of the model in understanding the factors that play a role in Employee Performance (Y). The remaining 4.7% of the variation may be influenced by other factors that have not been included in the study, such as leadership dynamics or other factors.

3.4 Goodness of Fit Model

SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Square Residual) evaluation, the standard is less than 0.1 to indicate the suitability of the model.

Table 4 Goodness of Fit Model

	Saturated model	Estimated model
SRMR	0.037	0.037
d_ULS	0.412	0.412
d_G	2.687	2.687
Chi-square	660.326	660.326
NFI	0.776	0.776

Source: Research Results, 2024

The SRMR value for the Saturated Model is 0.037, while for the Estimated Model is 0.037 as well. This shows that these two research models have SRMR values that are close to zero, which indicates a good fit.

3.5 Hypothesis Test

The hypothesis analysis in this study aims to evaluate the direct effect between variables as well as specific indirect effects through intermediate variables. Ghozali & Latan (2015) explained that in this analysis, direct and indirect influences were evaluated using *T-statistics* ($|O/STDEV|$) and *P-value*.

T-statistic ($|O/STDEV|$) It is used to measure how far the estimated values of Total Coefficient and Specific indirect effects (Original Sample, O) differ from the expected zero in the population. The greater the value of *the T-statistic*, the stronger the statistical evidence supporting the influence. On the other hand, *P-value* provides information about the statistical significance of the influence. The significance of the value (two-tailed) was tested using a significance level of 5% (0.05) and a T-value > 1.96 (Ghozali & Latan, 2015).

3.5.1 Direct Effect Test

Table 5 Direct Effect Test

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	Tstatistics ($ O/STDEV $)	Pvalues	Hipotesis
Kepuasan Kerja (Z) → Kinerja Pegawai (Y)	0.412	0.416	0.129	3.623	0.001	Diterima
Lingkungan Kerja (X1) → Kepuasan Kerja (Z)	0.615	0.601	0.115	5.335	0.000	Diterima
Lingkungan Kerja (X1) → Kinerja Pegawai (Y)	0.408	0.408	0.127	3.203	0.001	Diterima
Motivasi Kerja (X2) → Kepuasan Kerja (Z)	0.377	0.391	0.115	3.276	0.001	Diterima
Motivasi Kerja (X2) → Kinerja Pegawai (Y)	0.575	0.574	0.127	4.524	0.000	Diterima

Source: Research Results, 2024

Partially, there was a positive and significant influence between Work Environment (X1) and Job Satisfaction (Z), with *T statistics* of 5.335 and *P value* < 0.001. This first hypothesis was accepted

Partially, there was a positive and significant influence between Job Motivation (X2) and Job Satisfaction (Z), with *T statistics* of 3.276 and *P value* < 0.001. This second hypothesis is accepted.

Partially, there was a positive and significant influence between the Work Environment (X1) and Employee Performance (Y), with *T statistics* of 3.203 and *P value* < 0.001. This third hypothesis is accepted.

Partially, there was a positive and significant influence between Work Motivation (X2) and Employee Performance (Y), with *T statistics* of 4.524 and *P value* < 0.001. This fourth hypothesis is accepted.

Partially, there was a positive and significant influence between Job Satisfaction (Z) and Employee Performance (Y), with *T statistics* of 3.623 and *P value* < 0.001. This fifth hypothesis is accepted.

3.5.2 Indirect Effect Test

Table 6 Indirect Effect Test

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	Tstatistics (O/STDEV)	Pvalues	Hipotesis
Motivasi Kerja (X2) → Kepuasan Kerja (Z) → Kinerja Pegawai (Y)	0.642	0.648	0.176	5.557	0.000	Diterima
Lingkungan Kerja (X1) → Kepuasan Kerja (Z) → Kinerja Pegawai (Y)	0.069	0.067	0.109	0.628	0.530	Ditolak

Source: Research Results, 2024

Partially, there was a positive but insignificant influence between the Work Environment (X1) on Employee Performance (Y) through Job Satisfaction (Z), with *T statistics* of 0.628 and *P value* > 0.05. This sixth hypothesis was rejected.

Partially, there is a positive and significant influence of Work Motivation (X2) on Employee Performance (Y) through Job Satisfaction (Z), with *T statistics* of 5.557 and *P value* < 0.001. This seventh hypothesis is accepted.

4 Discussion

4.1 The Influence of Work Environment on Job Satisfaction at the Medan City Library and Archives Service

Partially, there was a positive and significant influence between Work Environment (X1) and Job Satisfaction (Z), with *T statistics* of 5.335 and *P value* < 0.001. This shows that the Work Environment, which includes aspects such as the workplace, infrastructure, cleanliness, lighting, tranquility, and working relationships between employees, has a significant impact on employee job satisfaction. Previous studies by Hasibuan (2018), Mangkunegara (2018), Kurniawan (2020), Solihatun et al (2021), and Sukaisih (2022) also confirmed that the Work Environment has a positive and significant impact on Job Satisfaction. A supportive work environment, including a comfortable workplace, adequate facilities and infrastructure, cleanliness, adequate lighting, and good working relationships between employees, can increase employee job satisfaction. Thus, supportive working conditions tend to make employees feel more satisfied with their work and personal life.

4.2 The Effect of Work Motivation on Job Satisfaction at the Medan City Library and Archives Office

Partially, there was a positive and significant influence between Job Motivation (X2) and Job Satisfaction (Z), with *T statistics* of 3.276 and *P value* < 0.001. This indicates that Work Motivation, which is the encouragement of the need in employees to adjust to the work environment and achieve goals, plays an important role in increasing employee job satisfaction. Previous research by Mangkunegara (2018), Sulistyowati et al (2017), and Garaika (2020) also showed that Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction. Adequate work motivation can encourage employees to feel satisfied with their work, because employees at the Medan City Library and Archives Service feel able to overcome challenges and achieve the desired goals.

4.3 The Influence of the Work Environment on Employee Performance at the Medan City Library and Archives Service

Partially, there was a positive and significant influence between the Work Environment (X1) and Employee Performance (Y), with *T statistics* of 3.203 and *P value* < 0.001. This shows that the Work Environment, which includes both physical and non-physical factors in the organization, has a significant impact on employee performance. Physical factors such as work equipment, temperature, noise, and workspace area can affect work comfort and efficiency, while

non-physical factors related to the relationship between employees, leaders, and subordinates also play an important role in shaping a work atmosphere that supports productivity. These findings are consistent with the results of previous research by Nugrahaningsih, & Julaela (2017) and Untung & Nugraheni (2017), which emphasized that the work environment affects the performance of employees or employees. Thus, a good working environment can help improve employee performance at the Medan City Library and Archives Service.

4.4 The Effect of Work Motivation on Employee Performance at the Medan City Library and Archives Service

Partially, there was a positive and significant influence between Work Motivation (X2) and Employee Performance (Y), with T statistics of 4.524 and P value < 0.001. This indicates that Work Motivation, which is an internal drive for employees to activate abilities, form skills, and achieve company goals, has a significant role in improving employee performance. The views of Siagian (2017) and Rivai (2015) reinforce this concept, where Work Motivation is considered an important factor in achieving performance that is in accordance with the role of the individual in the context of the company. Previous studies by Solihatun et al (2021) and Ingsih et al (2021) also support these findings, confirming that Work Motivation has a positive and significant relationship with employee performance. When an employee is motivated, a strong internal drive to achieve company goals encourages him to exhibit better, more creative, and more dedicated work behaviors. Thus, Work Motivation has a central role in influencing the performance of employees at the Medan City Library and Archives Service.

4.5 The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance at the Medan City Library and Archives Service

Partially, there was a positive and significant influence between Job Satisfaction (Z) and Employee Performance (Y), with T statistics of 3.623 and P value < 0.001. This shows that Job Satisfaction, which reflects an employee's subjective attitude towards his or her job and environment, has a significant impact on employee performance. Previous research by Lestari et al (2018) and Sulastiningtiyas et al (2018) also supports these findings, confirming that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. High job satisfaction tends to increase employee motivation, dedication, and commitment to their tasks. The relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance is mutually influencing, where high job satisfaction can trigger an increase in performance, and conversely, good performance can increase the level of job satisfaction. Thus, it is important for the Medan City Library and Archives Service to pay attention to the factors that affect employee job satisfaction in order to improve their performance.

4.6 The Influence of the Work Environment on Employee Performance at the Medan City Library and Archives Service Through Job Satisfaction

Partially, there was a positive but insignificant influence between the Work Environment (X1) on Employee Performance (Y) through Job Satisfaction (Z), with T statistics of 0.628 and P value > 0.05. This indicates that, although a conducive work environment can form the basis for improving employee job satisfaction, in this study there is no significant relationship between the work environment and employee performance through job satisfaction. However, factors such as adequate facilities, good working relationships, and support from superiors can still create conditions where employees feel comfortable and satisfied with their jobs.

4.7 The Significant Effect of Work Motivation on Employee Performance at the Medan City Library and Archives Service Through Job Satisfaction

Partially, there was a positive and significant influence of Work Motivation (X2) on Employee Performance (Y) through Job Satisfaction (Z), with T statistics of 5.557 and P value < 0.001. This indicates that Work Motivation has a strong impact on employee performance through the Job Satisfaction mechanism. Work Motivation, which is an internal drive for an employee to achieve goals and optimal performance, plays a crucial role in improving their performance. Job satisfaction, as a subjective evaluation of work and the work environment, also has a significant role in this relationship. Previous research by Fatmasari et al (2018) and Ameswari et al (2021) has shown that Work Motivation has a positive and significant impact on employee performance through a high level of job satisfaction. Thus, the dynamics between Job Motivation, Job Satisfaction, and Employee Performance form a series of interactions that affect each other.

5 Conclusion

Based on the results of this study, the following are relevant, detailed, and applicable suggestions to improve the performance and job satisfaction of employees at the Medan City Library and Archives Service:

- Improvement of the physical work environment such as the arrangement of the workspace by carrying out a work environment audit to identify areas that need improvement. Adjust the layout to make it more ergonomic

and comfortable, including improvements to lighting, ventilation, and hygiene. Furthermore, in work facilities, institutions can provide supporting facilities such as *pantries*, comfortable rest rooms, and modern work equipment that suits the needs of employees that can increase comfort and productivity.

- In order to improve the non-physical work environment related to the lowest question indicators of the respondents, namely independence in carrying out tasks (Mean: 3.77) and good communication between colleagues and leaders (Mean: 3.77), it is recommended to give more autonomy to employees in carrying out employee duties. In addition, it is necessary to develop programs or activities that support good, open, and smooth communication between colleagues and leaders, such as effective communication training, regular meetings, and the establishment of an open feedback mechanism. It is expected to increase productivity and welfare in the work environment.
- In strengthening work motivation, the implementation of award and recognition programs for employee performance such as TPP (Employee Income Allowance) ASN by the Regional Government to motivate the work of Employees of the Medan City Library and Archives Service.
- In job satisfaction, the results of the questionnaire show that one of the aspects of job satisfaction with the lowest score is "Do you feel that the work you do meets the expectations of the party who receives the results?" (Mean: 3.77). To improve the suitability of work results with recipients' expectations, the organization at the Medan City Library and Archives Service can provide focused training, such as training in archive management, software use, communication skills, and *public customer service*. This will help employees acquire the skills necessary to perform their duties better and ensure that the employee's work meets the expectations of the recipient.
- Optimizing employee performance by integrating the Archive Information System that is being developed by the Medan City Library and Archives Service. to support more effective management of libraries and archives so that employee performance can be more optimal.
- For future researchers, they can conduct follow-up research by adding relevant variables. This can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors that affect job satisfaction and employee performance at the Medan City Library and Archives Service. Variables such as leadership, organizational commitment, and others in the field of human resource management can make a scientific contribution to academics in the Master of Management Study Program at Panca Budi Development University.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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